

**DEFENSE MAPPING AGENCY
TECHNICAL ASSISTANCE
AT THE
AERONAUTICAL SYSTEMS DIVISION**

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ABSTRACT

Mapping, Charting and Geodetic (MC&G) products, and derivative data affecting targeting and navigation/position determination, must be considered at System Milestone Reviews. Furthermore, all System Concept Papers must include a discussion of MC&G requirements and issues affecting system development and subsequent operational deployment. The Defense Mapping Agency (DMA) has established a unique office (ASD/XR-DMA) that can increase the likelihood that these ambitious research and development requirements will be met. This office, located on-site at the Air Force Systems Command's Aeronautical Systems Division (ASD), provides working level MC&G technical assistance to Air Force aeronautical system developers. This paper outlines the variety of services the DMA Technical Assistance Office can provide to emerging digital cartographic data-dependent weapon systems. In addition, it describes several past instances where the office has provided invaluable MC&G support to ASD.

INTRODUCTION

Long before the DoD's current emphasis on Total Quality Management (TQM) and its accent on customer-supplier relationships, DMA and ASD had the foresight to establish an office at ASD to provide technical assistance for ASD users (customers) of DMA MC&G products. The impetus for this action was a 1972 DDR&E Memorandum to the Military Departments' Secretaries for R&D, encouraging the early involvement of DMA in weapon system development. In addition, it further reflected that, "review and approval of MC&G requirements would be included as a necessary part of the systems review process prior to initiation of systems development." In response to this, DMA obtained HQ AFSC (LGX) approval to establish a technical assistance office, run by the DMA Aerospace Center (DMAAC), to facilitate the interface between weapon system development and MC&G support. This office, collocated with ASD's Deputy Director for Development Planning (ASD/XR), would improve ASD capability in MC&G matters by providing on-site/full-time geodetic/cartographic expertise.

In its early years, this relationship worked well. For example, the DMA Technical Assistance Office provided invaluable support to the development of the cruise missile. This system is dependent, in large measure, on DMA's Terrain Contour Matching (TERCOM) data base for navigational updates. The DMA Technical Assistance Office provided data, specifications for the data and other pertinent cartographic information ensuring the simultaneous evolution of TERCOM and the weapon system that ultimately led to Initial Operational Deployment in 1982.

More recently, this goal of DMA involvement in weapon system development has been re-emphasized. Recent DoD memoranda stressed that MC&G products, and derivative data affecting targeting and navigation/position determination, must be considered at System Milestone Reviews. Moreover, all System Concept Papers must include a discussion of MC&G requirements and issues affecting system development and subsequent operational deployment. The DMA Technical Assistance Office was transferred to the DMA Systems Center, placing it in an organization chartered specifically to identify MC&G requirements early enough in the System's development cycle to ensure DMA product availability. It was then designated ASD/XR-DMA.

From the above, one can see that facilitating customer supplier intercourse, with regard to MC&G support for ASD is an idea that predates the present DoD TQM effort. However, recent experiences have led this writer to conclude that many of those involved in the acquisition of aerospace systems with MC&G requirements are not aware of DMA's presence at ASD. Therefore, in order to correct this perception, this paper seeks to improve the aerospace and electronics communities' awareness of ASD/XR—DMA. And, in keeping with one of the seven Quality Culture Fundamentals, to build strong, healthy customer/supplier relationships in areas pertaining to MC&G support for emerging aerospace systems.

This paper will outline the variety of services that ASD/XR-DMA can provide to emerging digital cartographic data-dependent weapon systems. Products, specifications and service support for users will be described in detail. In addition, descriptions of past instances where the office provided invaluable MC&G support to ASD will be provided. Armed with this information, developers of these systems will be better able to forge the strong customer/supplier partnership that effective TQM requires.

DMA TECHNICAL SUPPORT SERVICES

ASD/XR-DMA provides a multitude of services to the ASD community. The following lists several:

1. Disclosing product availability and geographic coverage.
2. Furthering the technical community's understanding of MC&G products.
3. Assistance in ordering maps, digital data and stating MC&G requirements.
4. Arranging formal MC&G training.

5. Providing technical area expertise to working groups and at design reviews.

6. Keeping DMA informed of future weapon system developments.

Product Availability and Geographic Coverage

Often, ASD users are not fully aware of what MC&G products are available. DMA produces standard products ranging from aeronautical charts and 1:50,000 topographic maps to Digital Terrain Elevation Data (DTED) and TERCOM, to name a few. In addition, other government agencies such as the Central Intelligence Agency (CIA) and the US Geological Survey (USGS) have cartographic information accessible to government users.

Secondly, users assume DMA products are worldwide in coverage. Regretfully, this is not the case. For example, aeronautical charts are only worldwide down to the 1:1,000,000 scale Operational Navigation Chart (ONC). Anything larger in scale has gaps mainly in areas remote to US interests. Moreover, given its demand on manpower and other resources, some digital data is even more limited in coverage.

The researcher/developer who bases schedule decisions on erroneous assumptions about the nature of MC&G products or their availability can negatively impact the program. This can be avoided by consulting with ASD/XR-DMA since it can provide advice and literature describing the various products available, and maintains the catalogs illustrating where, geographically, these products exist. In fact, ASD/XR-DMA recently prevented a highly visible laboratory effort from making schedule decisions based on misconceptions about DMA digital data coverage. They were briefed on DMA's present coverage and future production plans. As a result, the program effected changes early, and avoided any negative impacts.

Furthering the Technical Community's Understanding of MC&G Products

Once users know what products exist for their area of interest, ASD/XR-DMA can educate them on product characteristics such as information on scale, accuracy, data base structure (digital products) and other nuances. Those desiring more detailed MC&G technical information can obtain product specifications that specifically address cartographic production processes and standards. These specifications exist for every DMA product. In regard to digital MC&G products, the specifications provide a brief description of the products, their accuracy requirements and data/feature characteristics. This is followed by the digital file descriptions which make up the bulk of the digital product specifications. This latter section is important in understanding how the data is arranged in order to design the software to read and utilize the data. On the other hand, the product specifications for printed material provide specific information on compilation, symbology, color separation and photolithography procedures in addition to the descriptive type information found in the digital product specifications.

Specifications are the basis for understanding the foundations of particular MC&G products. However, many users

want to see demonstrations of the products and how they are used. To this end, in the spring of 1990, DMA unveiled its Warrior Support Center in Falls Church, Virginia. This facility will have displays set up for inspection by DoD users, developers and contractors. These displays will exhibit DMA standard and prototype products, and how the products are utilized. ASD/XR-DMA will publicize the Warrior Support Center capabilities at ASD and coordinate ASD users' visits to the center.

In order to stay fully abreast of recent developments in MC&G data products and uses, ASD/XR-DMA interacts regularly with AFSC's Rome Air Development Center (RADC), the US Army's Engineer Topographic Laboratories (ETL), the Naval Oceanographic Atmospheric Research and Development Laboratory (NOARL), the US Army Engineer Waterways Experiment Station and others. Moreover, ASD/XR-DMA tracks cartographic experimentation done in academia so that this valuable source of information is tapped for the benefit of the ASD community. In these ways, ASD/XR-DMA serves as a clearinghouse for this information, facilitating interaction between the ASD user community and scientists in these other government laboratories.

MC&G Ordering Assistance and Requirements Submission

After users make MC&G product selections, ASD/XR-DMA expedites product delivery. DMA-produced paper maps, charts and other printed information can be ordered through the office's automatic initial distribution (AID) account. In addition, the office will also prepare the necessary correspondence to CIA and/or USGS in order to obtain these products. Recent attempts to apply TQM, and statistically measure previous product deliveries, has resulted in ASD/XR-DMA obtaining these items for customers in 15-21 days. Digital MC&G data orders take longer as these requests must be coordinated through AFSC and HQ USAF before they reach DMA. This is in accordance with AFR 96-3 "Ordering and Stocking Maps, Charts, and Related Materials." (See Figure 1 for an outline of this process.) However, ASD/XR-DMA accelerates the process by assisting with the preparation of order forms and cover letters required for digital data orders. ASD/XR-DMA also assists ASD users in submitting their MC&G product requirements through AFSC to DMA as part of the POM process.

DIGITAL DATA COORDINATION PROCESS

Arranging Formal MC&G Training

For those at ASD already well informed on DMA product characteristics and ordering procedures, there are formal training programs available to expand their knowledge in this area. ASD/XR-DMA has course descriptions, the class calendar and can coordinate the scheduling of Defense Mapping School (DMS) courses for ASD eligibles.

Interest is greatest for the following courses:

- Mapping, Charting and Geodetic Staff Officer Course
- Introduction to Digital Data
- Multispectral Imagery
- Geographic Information Systems
- Analytical Photogrammetric Positioning System I (APPS I)

ASD/XR-DMA has been instrumental in getting several ASD personnel to these courses. Nevertheless, space is limited, and user funding often prohibits attending sessions at DMS. Therefore, ASD/XR-DMA hosts a DMS Mobile Training Team (MTT) biennially at ASD in September. The MTT addresses various topics taken from the courses listed above and tailors it for the ASD audience. These have been well received, with over 60 persons attending each of the last two programs.

Providing Technical Expertise To Working Groups/Design Reviews

Increasingly, modern weapon systems and related support equipment are depending on MC&G data as integral components. Therefore, at many system design reviews and data base working groups, questions about MC&G data and action items pertaining to that data are raised. If DMA is not represented, these questions may be inadequately resolved and may grow into large problems by system milestones.

At a working group for a fighter aircraft weapons system trainer, ASD/XR-DMA found the program experiencing difficulty in ordering maps requiring special handling not explained in the catalogs they were consulting. ASD/XR-DMA intervened and obtained what was needed in time to avoid any delays. On another occasion, a working group was trying to decide what map features to digitize in order to enhance a DMA digital features data base. However, their approach was unscientific. ASD/XR-DMA pointed out that DMA researchers had already conducted a similar but more systematic analysis and coordinated a dialogue between the DMA personnel and the working group. This saved over 40 man-hours of unnecessary effort.

Design reviews are no different. ASD/XR-DMA normally performs part, or all, of the six services discussed in this paper at these meetings and departs with several action items related to these areas.

Keeping DMA Informed of Future Weapon System Developments

It is in this area that ASD/XR-DMA can more fully achieve the goals of the DoD memoranda to insure early DMA involvement in weapon system development. In 1988, DMA received a proof of concept system called the DMA Requirements Analysis System (DMARAS). This system, maintained by ASD/XR-DMA's parent organization, the DMA Systems Center Advanced Weapons and Systems Division, was designed to "consolidate and access MC&G requirements within and across service lines from information acquired from customers." The proof of concept, DMARAS, demonstrated the capability to:

1. Build and maintain a comprehensive Advanced Weapons and Systems (AWS) data base.
2. Perform queries, mostly on requirements-related data.
3. Produce hardcopy and, in the future, softcopy output of queries.
4. Generate/create graphics associated with an advanced weapon system.
5. Track relevant documentation and correspondence.

The benefits of DMARAS to the developer/user community of MC&G products are threefold:

1. "Compromise" products can be produced for separate users of the same type of MC&G product. Thus, scarce fiscal resources are preserved.
2. If the "compromise" product is a DMA standard, then, further funds can be saved.
3. DMARAS could be used to direct developers to less expensive options that will result in little or no degradation in the weapon/system function through the use of sensitivity analysis software.

Given its geographic location, and the relationships the DMA Technical Assistance office has developed at ASD, it obtains and forwards much of the information on emerging aerospace systems that populates the DMARAS AWS data base.

CONCLUSION

By performing these six services, ASD/XR-DMA ensures that ASD's needs for MC&G products and information are fulfilled while DMA is kept informed of the data requirements of emerging aerospace systems. Facilitating this information flow achieves the goal DMA and AFSC established when the office was created and keeps it relevant in this age of TQM where customer-supplier teamwork and trust are paramount. In describing these services, this paper has improved the aerospace and electronic communities' awareness of ASD/XR-DMA and facilitated the exploration and expansion of cartographic data uses.

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